

philosophical proof of Fermat's Theorem

16.11.2024, Denisov Ivan

Russia, Denissoviv@yandex.ru

Fermat's Last Theorem (also called "Fermat's Great Theorem" or "Fermat's Last Theorem") states that for any natural number $n > 2$, the equation $x^n + y^n = z^n$ has no solutions in positive integers x, y, z .

Proof

The equation $x^n + y^n = z^n$ can be written as follows: $x^n + y^n = r^n$.

This is the equation for the length of a segment r through its coordinates in n -dimensional space.

Since the equation for r^n only has coordinates x and y , it turns out that the solution to the original equation is a circle in the OXY plane.

Thus, it will be true: $x^n + y^n = x^2 + y^2$ and $r^n = r^2$. Because in the OXY plane, the length of a segment r is expressed as follows: $x^2 + y^2 = r^2$.

Thus, the solution to the original equation will be the same roots of the second-order equation.

The conditions of Fermat's Theorem will be satisfied when: $r^n = r^2$, $x^n = x^2$, $y^n = y^2$.

The solution to the equation $r^n = r^2$ is $r=1$, because by the condition $n>2$ and x, y, z are positive numbers.

This can be true when $(x;y) = (0;1)$ or $(1;0)$, and the triple of numbers will look like this: $(x;y;z) = (0;1;1)$ or $(1;0;1)$.

By Fermat's condition $x \neq y \neq z$.

Therefore, the problem is solved: for any natural number $n > 2$, the equation $x^n + y^n = z^n$ has no solutions in positive integers x, y, z